

Popular Article

Conservation of animal genetic resources in India-Public aspect

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Abstract

Breeds contain the genetic diversity of domesticated species; hence conserving breeds conserve this diversity. Breeds are stable genetic resources that enable the matching of animals with various environments and production goals. Breeds were created by a process involving foundation, isolation and selection. Breed types that are considered genetic resources include "landraces" (local breeds), standard breeds, commercial production breeds and feral livestock that has converted to a free-living state.

Why do need conservation

1. Maintaining breed diversity for future requirements,
2. cultural ties between people and breeds
3. Maintain resources for scientific research
4. A number of breeds have undergone genetic modifications that specifically equip them to particular difficult situations
5. Protecting them with a solid genetic basis,
6. Maintaining their long-term survival with a market for the breed

Methods of conservation

1. In-situ conservation

In this method animal kept in own breeding area and their adaptive environment.

- a. Live animal
- b. Institutional herd
- c. Farmer flock
- d. Genetic improvement and management of herd

2. Ex-situ conservation

- a. In-vivo ex-situ conservation

When ex-situ conservation followed in research institute, zoo.

- b. In-vitro ex-situ conservation

When ex-situ conservation performed in form of cryo preservation of tissue, embryo, sperm and clone.

Conclusion

In the context of animal breeding, conservation genetics deals with issues of the preservation of rare and endangered breeds or populations, as well as the use of intentional genetic alteration to increase the viability, productivity, and efficiency of production. The preservation of uncommon and endangered breeds is a major concern in the developed world, where numerous organizations are dedicated to this goal.

Reference

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